

Screening rice germplasm against *Fusarium sheath rot* (ShR) disease

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We screened 34 cultivars and lines against the *Fusarium* ShR organism *Fusarium moniliforme* Sheld. in the field and in the pot house under artificial inoculation. A spore suspension of the pathogen was sprayed to injured boot leaf sheaths in the pot house and to uninjured boot leaf sheaths in the field.

Disease severity was scored on a 0-4 scale: 0 = no infection; 1 = small brown lesions on boot leaf sheath, some lesions enlarge and coalesce to cover about 25% of the leaf sheath, normal panicle emergence and grain filling; 2 = lesions cover about half the sheath with incomplete panicle exertion, glumes discolored, sterile spikelets; 3 = lesions cover 65% of sheath, panicle struggles to emerge, more than 50% sterile spikelets, severe glume discoloration; and 4 = entire sheath rotted, no panicle emergence, or if panicle emerges, no grain filling.

Cultivars or lines that showed no disease in the field were infected in the

Reaction of rice cultivars or lines to *F. moniliforme*. Ludhiana, India, 1985-86.

Mean disease severity score	Cultivar or lines	
	Field	Pot house
0	1254, 1255, 1259, 1272, 1326, 1336, Bas. 370, Pb. Bas. 1	—
0-1	1168, 1169, 1170, 1173, 1175, 1180, 1195, 1197, 1201, 1202, 1203, 1204, 1205, 1210, 1213, 1249, 1253, 1337, 1352, 1353, PR4141, PR103, IR8	1168, 1169, 1170, 1180, 1195, 1197, 1202, 1203, 1204, 1210, 1213, 1245, 1249, 1253, 1272, 1326, 1336, 1337, 1352, 1353, PR4141, PR103, Bas. 370, Pb. Bas. 1, IR8
1-2	1245, Palman Jaya	579, 1175, 1201, Palman 579
2-3	—	1173, Jaya
3-4	PR106	PR106

pot house (see table). None of the cultivars or lines tested were immune, but disease severity in the pot house was lowest in the lines that showed no infection in the field. Even though most

lines or cultivars were infected, panicle emergence and grain filling were normal. Some high-yielding cultivars (Jaya and PR106) were most susceptible. □

Background resistance to bacterial blight (BB): lesion expansion

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A cultivar's background resistance to BB can be demonstrated indirectly by comparing its relative resistance index to races 1 and 2 of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*. The index was determined from hill and leaf infection of IR cultivars compared to susceptible check IR24.

We analyzed lesion expansion on infected leaves as an indicator of background resistance. Component measurements may show differences in resistance among IR cultivars possessing the *Xa-4* gene. Six races of the BB pathogen and IR20, IR22, IR26, IR36, IR42, IR48, IR54, IR58, and IR62, all known to carry *Xa-4*, were examined.

Plants were raised in pots in the greenhouse, with two replications/cultivar arranged in a split-split-plot design. Plantings were staggered at 20-d intervals to synchronize inoculation.

Resistance or susceptibility to BB of IR cultivars on the basis of mean lesion area at 15 d after inoculation. Expressed in relation to resistance of susceptible check IR24^a to virulent and avirulent races of *X. c. pv. oryzae*.

Variety	Relative resistance ^b (%)					
	Avirulent race			Virulent race		
	PXO61	PXO112	PXO71	PXO86	PXO79	PXO99
	20 DAS					
IR26	66.3 a	45.2 a	51.1 a	0.4 b	2.6 a	0.0 a
IR22	63.6 ab	34.9 a	7.5 c	0.0 b	-14.2 a	0.5 a
IR20	62.9 ab	40.6 a	18.9 abc	2.3 b	-6.1 a	5.1 a
IR54	61.8 ab	52.7 a	44.5 ab	20.8 ab	7.8 a	1.7 a
IR58	61.2 ab	41.2 a	37.8 abc	3.9 b	-3.4 a	0.0 a
IR48	60.1 ab	40.0 a	40.2 abc	42.8 a	4.7 a	0.7 a
IR36	51.2 ab	40.9 a	10.0 bc	-0.2 b	-8.1 a	0.0 a
IR42	48.9 ab	43.4 a	16.5 abc	23.3 ab	-0.4 a	0.5 a
IR62	27.4 b	39.9 a	25.3 abc	18.0 ab	3.8 a	0.0 a
	40 DAS					
IR54	40.9 a	28.1 a	29.7 ab	12.4 a	2.0 a	26.8 a
IR26	37.8 a	26.1 a	37.4 a	-0.9 ab	-1.6 a	15.3 ab
IR20	36.9 a	23.1 a	23.1 abc	3.8 ab	-2.4 a	12.6 ab
IR58	36.4 a	17.7 a	27.3 abc	7.7 ab	-6.6 a	5.7 bc
IR22	35.2 a	23.5 a	34.4 a	-2.4 b	-0.1 a	15.6 ab
IR48	35.1 a	23.2 a	13.8 bc	10.5 ab	3.6 a	12.5 ab
IR42	34.4 a	27.9 a	13.6 bc	6.5 ab	-4.4 a	6.8 ab
IR36	34.4 a	20.8 a	20.3 abc	-3.6 b	-5.1 a	10.1 bc
IR62	31.8 a	20.9 a	11.5 c	-0.1 ab	-8.4 a	-2.2 c
	60 DAS					
IR54	19.5 a	19.8 a	19.3 a	11.4 a	7.5 a	20.7 a
IR26	19.5 a	19.4 a	18.7 a	0.2 a	-1.2 a	14.9 ab
IR22	19.5 a	20.2 a	13.3 a	-0.6 a	3.1 a	8.4 ab
IR58	18.7 a	19.4 a	14.5 a	-0.4 a	-0.1 a	7.7 b
IR48	17.5 a	15.4 a	12.2 a	6.1 a	7.9 a	11.6 ab
IR36	17.1 a	13.5 a	9.5 a	-2.4 a	-3.3 a	4.3 b
IR62	16.6 a	18.4 a	7.3 a	-0.1 a	-2.4 a	11.6 ab
IR42	16.2 a	16.2 a	9.9 a	-1.3 a	0.9 a	10.3 ab
IR20	13.4 a	15.6 a	16.0 a	4.0 a	4.1 a	8.4 ab

^aEstimated on basis of lesion area. ^b0 = as susceptible as IR24, + = more resistant, - = more susceptible. In a column, treatment means for each DAS having a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at the 5% level.